

SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL BASIS OF TEACHING UZBEK LITERATURE

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Abstract: In this article, the theory and technologies of teaching literature, teaching methods are discussed.

Keywords: Uzbek language and literature, knowledge, interactive method, technologies, efficiency, innovation, self-education, creative activity.

At present, almost all developed countries of the world have realized the need to reform their education systems so that the student becomes the central figure in the educational process, so that the cognitive activity of the student is in the center of attention of teachers. The system of continuous education is the imperative of the times. In recent years, in connection with the differentiation of education, the emergence of the work of schools and classes of various profile orientations, including humanitarian, mathematical, technical, economic, lyceum schools, gymnasium schools, questions about the goals, content, forms and methods of teaching the Russian language at school. Currently, an increasing number of teachers are using non-traditional lessons in their work. It is thanks to this extraordinary content, methods and forms that the lesson gives the necessary acceleration to the development of the individual. Non-traditional lessons in the school began to occupy a significant place. We believe that conducting lessons of this form is always advantageous, because they present not only game moments, original presentation of the material, the employment of students not only in preparing lessons, but also in conducting the lessons themselves through various forms of collective and group work. Interactive ("Inter" is mutual, "act" is to act) means to interact, is in the mode of conversation, dialogue with someone. Interactive and active methods have much in common. Unlike active methods, interactive ones are focused on a wider interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and on the dominance of student activity in the learning process. Interactive methods include the following: discussion, heuristic conversation,

brainstorming, role-playing, "business" games, trainings, case method, project method, group work with illustrative material, discussion of videos, etc. At present, the problem of using interactive methods is relevant, since the uniformity and stereotype of lessons reduce interest in learning, make the learning process boring and unpromising. And in elementary school, such lessons are generally unacceptable. Literature is one of the most interesting subjects in school. Therefore, it is necessary to develop students' interest in this subject even in elementary school, to make it as joyful and exciting as possible. This is where interactive methods, didactic games, and their periodic use in the classroom can help. Here it is also necessary to pay attention to the fact that students make the transition from playing activity to learning, at primary school age, learning activity becomes the leading one, but the game and interactive methods also take place at this age. This is evidenced by the fact that children continue to bring toys to school. Based on this feature in the development of younger students, we can conclude that it is through didactic games that you can draw the attention of children to the subject, develop their interest, interest in gaining knowledge.

One of the methods of active learning of the Uzbek language and literature using interactive technologies is problem-based learning, project method, business games, integrated lessons, etc. To enhance the cognitive activity of students in computer science lessons, I consider it appropriate to present the educational material in a multimedia and interactive form. Such material can be represented as: Presentations, which, with their help, can illustrate the material, and you can provide students with the opportunity to independently study; computer games that contain educational or educational material; Hypertext applications that may contain test benches; test environments; interactive programs, the more student takes part in the learning process, the acquired knowledge, abilities and skills gain more significance; graphic demonstration materials, these can be like ordinary posters, stands, handouts, or better, if these are images that the student himself will find and view; videos. In teaching the Uzbek language and literature, as well as other subjects, educational project and research activities are widely used. A training project involves a set of actions independently performed by students to solve a problem significant to them, associated with the collection and processing of material and the presentation of the finished product in electronic form. The teacher, in turn, helps the student navigate the electronic resources, gives advice on finding and selecting information material. Classes using interactive technologies, including

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multimedia presentations, allow students to visually learn the teaching material. Multimedia presentations in teaching computer science provide: intensification of instruction, student activity, individualization of instruction, development of autonomy, increased motivation, etc.

The search for ways to train competitive specialists allows us to conclude that it is currently important to be able to uncover the abilities and opportunities in mastering the profession. In our opinion, the effectiveness of training depends on: understanding and taking into account the individual characteristics of individuals and the age of the trainees; from the communicative skills of the teacher, contributing to the creation of an environment of cooperation; from an arsenal of technologies that activate students, teach them better perception and memorization of information, solving professional problems. As already noted, the possession of interactive methods and their application in practice in the education system gives positive dynamics, as the work goes to the "group result", which in turn improves the perception of information received and worked out in groups. I think that in the process of studying linguistic disciplines, testing and using innovative interactive teaching methods, which, unfortunately, have not yet found an adequate "response" among the pedagogical community, will undoubtedly find application. In conclusion, it can be argued that the use of interactive technologies in the study of the Uzbek language replaces many traditional teaching aids. The teacher of any language should not forget that his main task is the development of a socially significant and value-oriented personality, the training of students in mental work, which is more important than the transfer of finished knowledge. An analysis of new trends in optimizing the educational process at school allows us to say that for learning it is important not only to transfer knowledge, but also to instill skills and abilities to independently find and analyze new information, evaluate and apply it, reasonably argue, establish causal relationships, develop abilities of continuous self-education.

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